

Title: Prevalence, risk factors, and clinical course of iliac aneurysms – a sub study of the population based DANCAVAS trials: Risk factor divergence in iliac artery aneurysms with vs without concomitant aorta aneurysms

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Introduction

Aneurysmal disease is generally defined as a localized 50% increase of the artery's diameter compared to expected diameter and can occur at any artery in the body. The most common site of aneurysmal disease is in the abdominal part of the aorta. The knowledge of the abdominal aortic aneurysmal disease (AAA) is increasing as more countries introduce screening programs, however there is still a lack of knowledge regarding other sites of aneurysmal disease such as iliac artery aneurysms (IAA). The most common localization of IAAs is in the common iliac artery (CIA) but can occur in the internal and the external iliac artery as well. For CIA a size of ≥ 18 mm in men and ≥ 15 mm in women and for the internal iliac artery ≥ 8 mm is considered aneurysmatic (1).

The exact prevalence of AAA is still subject of discussion, as new studies show prevalence of $< 1\%$ in 65-year-olds of Sweden and UK based on findings of their screening programs (2). The DANCAVAS trials show a prevalence of 5.1% overall and 3.7% in the 65-year-old men. Even more dissent is present regarding prevalence and incidence of IAA, where the isolated IAA occurs with an incidence of 0.4-1.9% in dated literature, however the DANCAVAS study found a prevalence of 2.3% of the screened population. Of these only 11% will present without concomitant AAA, even though the prevalence of IAA in AAA patients varies from 15-40% (1, 3-4).

Regarding screening modality, ultrasound is recommended for AAAs due to its high sensitivity (95%) and specificity (100%) for the detection (5), whereas the sensitivity for ultrasound in identifying IAAs is 69% (5). CTA is the most accurate imaging modality in detection of IAAs, however ultrasound as the primary choice of imaging is recommended (1, 5). The recommendations for imaging surveillance for IAA are every three years for aneurysms 20-24 mm in diameter, every two years for aneurysms 25-29 mm in diameter, and yearly for aneurysms ≥ 30 mm in diameter.

IAAs are often diagnosed at an asymptomatic stage but can present with rupture at time of diagnosis or as symptomatic (1). Symptoms can vary from local compression of pelvic structures such as nerves, the ureter, or iliac vein which could lead to delay of diagnosis (5).

The reasons for development of aneurysmal disease are due to a series of causes both acquired and inherited risks. For IAA the risk factors strongly present in the patient group are smoking and hypertension, whereas for AAA the predominantly risk factors include smoking as well, but also

familiar history of aneurysmal disease (4). The majority of IAA patients are male (90%) and the disease is diagnosed after the age of 70 (1).

Currently the threshold for elective repair of IAAs is 4 cm as ruptures are rarely seen in aneurysms smaller than that. Reported growth rates of IAA are similar to AAA and estimated to 1-4 mm/year depending on diameter of the aneurysm (1). Known risk factors influencing IAA progression, as well as knowledge on medical therapies in terms of blood pressure control or treatment with platelet inhibitors, beta blockers, or statins in patients with isolated IAA is lacking. Therefore, the current recommendations follow those stated for AAA (1).

The paucity of current evidence regarding IAA risk factors begs the question whether the risk factors for the development of IAA, both isolated and concomitant with AAA, are the same as for AAA. This prospective study, based on DANCAVAS data enriched with Danish registry data, therefore seeks to clarify whether there are convergences in risk factors related to the development of IAA with or without the presence of AAA.

Furthermore, we intended to estimate contemporary IAA incidence rates, progression rates as well as rupture risk for these aneurysms.

As well as describing patients' clinical course, including progression to repair, potential rupture, major adverse cardiovascular and lower limb events, and mortality, in comparison with individuals with AAA without IAA and with the background population.

Aims

- 1) Describe the prevalence and risk factors for IAA, overall and stratified by coexisting AAA
- 2) Describe their growth rates and risk factors for progression
- 3) Describe IAA's clinical course to repair, rupture, major adverse cardiac events (MACE), major adverse limb events (MALE), and overall mortality

Material

14,994 60-74-year-old male attenders to non-contrast CT-scanning in the DANCAVAS randomized clinical trials

Methods

Data is stored at The Danish Health Data Authority, baseline variables are used as in the protocol paper, follow up data as in the 5-year benefit paper (NEJM 2023) and will be analyzed using R 4.5.2

Statistical Analysis Plan

Data management: Participants are classified into isolated iliac artery aneurysm (IAA-only), IAA with concomitant AAA (IAA+AAA), AAA without IAA (AAA-only) and background population (without IAA and AAA).

Clinical characteristics will be stated in a table of baseline characteristics comprising age, smoking, hypertension, diabetes, family history of aneurysm, cardiovascular comorbidities, medication use, blood pressure, BMI, total Cholesterol, HbA1C, eGFR>60 mL/min/1.73 m², maximal infrarenal aortic diameter and coronary artery calcification (CAC) score. The stated baseline strata will be compared using Pearsons χ^2 for categorical variables and t-test/Wilcoxon for continuous variables.

Multivariable logistic regression will be carried out based on the already known risk factors to AAA to identify risk factors for IAA and to compare associations between IAA-only vs IAA+AAA.

Growth rates for aneurysm diameter change (mm/year) will be assessed by linear mixed-effects models including baseline diameter and identified risk factors.

Incidence of need for repair, rupture, MACE, MALE and death will be assessed through Crude and adjusted Cox proportional hazards for time-to-repair/rupture/death with stratified survival analysis by IAA-only vs IAA+AAA, AAA without IAA and the background population without IAA or AAA. The adjusted analysis will use the above identified risk factors.

Time frame

Since all data is available, it would be feasible to assume that data can be analyzed within the next 2-3 months, in the meantime a manuscript could be drafted, aiming for abstract submission to ESVS 1st of Maj 26, and a submission to a peer reviewed journal within the next 6 months.

Literature

- (1) ESVS 2024 Management Guidelines of Abdominal Aorto-iliac Artery Aneurysm
- (2) Wanhainen A et al.: "Continued Declining Prevalence of Screening Detected Abdominal Aortic Aneurysms in 65 Year Old Swedish Men"
- (3) Lindholt JS et al: "Five-Year Outcomes of the Danish Cardiovascular Screening (DANCAVAS) Trial"
- (4) Rutherford's Vascular Surgery and Endovascular Therapy, 10th ed
- (5) Corneli M et Perea GO: "Which patients should we screen to detect an aneurysm of the abdominal aorta?" European Society of Cardiology, E-journal of Cardiology Practice, 2020;No. 29 vol 18 (6)
Sandhu RS, Pipinos II. Isolated iliac artery aneurysms. Semin Vasc Surg 2005;18:209e15.